

EFFECT OF AUTOLOGOUS PLATELET-RICH PLASMA (PRP) IN THE TREATMENT OF HERPETIC KERATITIS**Sultanova M.M.***MD, PhD.,**Azerbaijan Institute of Postgraduate Education after A.Aliyev, Baku, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

Purpose: to research the results of PRP-therapy in the treatment of herpetic keratitis (HK).

Materials and methods. We research the results of PRP-therapy in the treatment of herpetic keratitis in 16 patients (23 eyes). The patients were divided into 2 groups. In the first group (11 children, 16 eyes - 70%), patients received standard HK treatment, patients of the second group (5 children, 7 eyes - 30%) also received PRP-therapy.

Results. In the 2-nd group of children faster and more stable results were obtained compared to patients of the 1st group. The average index of corneal damage at admission in patients, received standard HK treatment, averaged 14.7. In children, received PRP-therapy, it was 15.3, respectively. On the 5th day after the start of treatment, the average corneal lesion index was 8.2 in the first group and 5.9 in the second. On the 10th day after the start of treatment, the corneal lesion index decreased to 6.3 in the first group and 3.1 in the second. When the damaged surface was stained with fluorescein on the 15th day of therapy in 6 eyes (37.5%) of the 1st group and in 5 eyes (71.4%) of the 2nd group, complete epithelialization was observed, the lesion index was 1.2 in patients of group 1 and 0.8 in children of group 2.

Conclusion. Using of PRP-therapy in the herpetic keratitis treatment allows to get faster and more stable results than in patients receiving standard treatment. This method is safely, without toxic reactions and local allergic complications and could be recommended in the treatment of herpetic keratitis in children.

Keywords: herpetic keratitis, PRP-therapy

The problem of corneal disease continues to be one of the serious problems throughout the world. According to WHO, more than 40% of patients with keratitis become visually impaired, which accounts for 4-5% of all causes of blindness [1]. According to the etiology of corneal lesions, viruses of the Herpesviridae family come first [2]. The latter are DNA-containing viruses that persist in the host's body for life. The high incidence of herpes infection is evidenced by data from seroepidemiological studies: antibodies to the herpes simplex virus are found in the blood of 90-100% of the adult population of the globe [2,3]

Up to 1.5 million new cases of herpetic keratitis (HK) are diagnosed annually in the world [2,3]. Currently, there is a more severe course of herpesvirus diseases of the eye. The latter are characterized by a tendency to the recurrent nature of the course, which exacerbates the social significance of this problem. In pediatric practice, herpetic keratitis accounts for up to 70% of all corneal lesions. According to a number of authors, up to 30% of herpetic eye lesions are resistant to antiviral drugs.

There are publications in the literature on the use of platelet-rich autoplasm (PRP) in ophthalmology. This technique belongs to the field of regenerative medicine and is widely used in stomatology, maxillofacial, plastic, cardiovascular surgery, reconstructive orthopedics, endocrinology [4,5,6,7]. To date, there is no single algorithm for the use of PRP in ophthalmology, the time and duration of therapy are not determined depending on the severity of clinical manifestations. Despite this, PRP is certainly of great interest to practitioners, given its high therapeutic efficacy, ease of obtaining autoplasm, the potential possibilities of its use, as well as a fairly low cost [5,7].

Purpose of the work: to research the results of PRP therapy in the treatment of herpetic keratitis.

Materials and methods. We retrospectively analyzed the outpatient records of 16 children (23 eyes) who were diagnosed with herpetic keratitis at the outpatient department of the National Ophthalmological Center named after Z.Aliyeva from September 2021 to March 2022. All patients underwent routine ophthalmological examinations: visometry, tonometry, biomicroscopy using fluorescein staining, and ophthalmoscopy. The retina and optic nerve were visualized by inverse ophthalmoscopy using a slit lamp. Biomicroscopy of discharge from the eye was prescribed, culture for the presence of microflora, and sensitivity to antimicrobial drugs was determined. Children did not previously receive any eye drops for 24 hours. A general blood test was performed to determine the presence of infections, immunoglobulins (Ig) class M and G, herpes types I and II, and cytomegalovirus. All patients were examined by a pediatrician. In 9 patients (56%) a monocular process was observed, in 7 children (44%) the disease developed in both eyes. The patients were divided into 2 groups. In the first group (11 children, 16 eyes - 70%), patients received standard treatment of HK, patients of the second group (5 people, 7 eyes - 30%) were also prescribed injections of PRP 2.5 ml retrobulbar. After confirmation of the diagnosis, the following treatment was prescribed: local ganciclovir in the form of ointment, instillation of interferon, mydriatic, tobramycin or another antibiotic, depending on the results of sensitivity to antimicrobial drugs. Dexamethasone with ceftriaxone was administered parabolbar. Vitamin C was prescribed intravenously, acyclovir was prescribed orally in an age-appropriate dosage, and multivitamins. Patients of the second group, along with standard therapy, were prescribed 2.5 ml parabolbar injections of autoplasm.

The results were assessed on days 5, 10, 15 after the start of treatment based on visual acuity and biomicroscopic picture of the anterior segment of the eye. The area of fluorescein staining of the damaged surface was estimated according to the National Eye Institute (NEI) 5-zone corneal model. According to this model, zone 1 corresponds to the center of the cornea and has a round shape, and zones 2-5 (upper, temporal, nasal and lower) are, respectively, 4 equal-sized segments around the central zone. The degree of staining of each sector in the 5-zonal corneal model is assessed on a 4-point scale (0 - no staining; 1 - traces of staining; 2 - weak staining; 3 points - moderate staining; 4 - pronounced staining) and is carried out according to the Efron system, developed in 1997. The maximum total number of points in this system is 20.

Results. The condition of the cornea at admission and in dynamics depending on the group is reflected in Table 1. The average index of corneal lesion at admission in patients of the first group averaged 14.7, in children of the 2nd group – 15.3, respectively. The optical part of the cornea was affected in all children, and corneal edema was observed. Patients of both groups were

diagnosed with herpetic keratitis, confirmed by the presence of high blood levels of Ig M and G herpes type I and II, or cytomegalovirus. Examination of the discharge from the conjunctival cavity revealed the presence of a virus.

On the 5th day after the start of treatment, the average corneal lesion index was 8.2 in the first group and 5.9 in the second. Patients of the first and second groups showed weakly positive dynamics with the gradual disappearance of epithelial defects. The damage area decreased slightly in both groups, but in the second group there was a more pronounced improvement. There was also a decrease in edema, conjunctival injection, and photophobia. On the 10th day after the start of treatment, the corneal lesion index decreased to 6.3 in the first group and 3.1 in the second. When staining the damaged surface with fluorescein on day 15 of therapy, complete epithelialization was observed in 6 eyes (37.5%) of the first group and 5 eyes (71.4%) of the second group, the lesion index was 1.2 in patients of group 1 and 0.8 in children of group 2.

Table 1.

Changes in the condition of the cornea in patients with HK at admission and during treatment.

	The average corneal lesion index			
	at the time of admission	5 day	10 day	15 day
1 group, 11 child (16 eyes)	14,7	8,2	6,3	1,2
2 group, 5 child (7 eyes)	15,3	5,9	3,1	0,8

Notes: $p < 0,05$

The changes in visual acuity of patients with HK during treatment are presented in Table 2. As can be seen from the table, the visual acuity of children at the initial treatment averaged 0.1 in both groups. The higher the corneal lesion index was observed, the lower the vision was. On the 5th day after the start of treatment, visual acuity was 0.2 in patients of group 1 and

0.3 in the second. On the 10th day of therapy, in children in the group with standard therapy, vision rose to 0.3-0.4, whereas in patients who received PRP therapy, visual acuity was 0.5-0.6. On the 15th day of treatment, the vision of patients in the second group rose to 0.8-0.9 versus 0.5-0.6 in patients of the first group.

Table 2.

Changes in visual acuity in patients with GK at admission and during treatment.

	Average visual acuity			
	at the time of admission	5 day	10 day	15 day
1 group, 11 child (16 eyes)	0,1	0,2	0,3-0,4	0,5-0,6
2 group, 5 child (7 eyes)	0,1	0,3	0,5-0,6	0,8-0,9

Notes: $p < 0,01$

In all cases, patients receiving PRP therapy had a positive reaction to the administration of the drug. There were no cases of an allergic reaction. There was a slight edema of the lower eyelid, as a reaction to the introduction of plasma. The swelling disappeared in a short time. The technique has proven to be safe and effective. Further observation showed that more stable results were obtained in the second group. The observation demonstrated the absence of relapses in patients receiving PRP therapy. Among the patients of the first group, 8 children (10 eyes, 62.5%) experienced an ex-

acerbation of symptoms during the year. Repeated violation of the integrity of the corneal epithelium was diagnosed in 4 eyes (25%, 2 children), and a relapse of keratitis was diagnosed. However, in order to obtain statistically reliable data, further monitoring of patients is necessary.

Discussions. In the literature available to us, the authors point to the beneficial effects of plasma therapy on human body tissues [1,6,7]. Platelet mass plays the main role in PRP therapy. It contains growth factors that stimulate the appearance of new cells. When injected into damaged tissues, platelets cause its cells to

actively divide. This leads to accelerated regeneration, which stimulates the healing process of the tissue. Thus, PRP therapy is based on the principle of self-healing of affected cells and tissues. Our research confirms the conclusions given by the researchers.

Conclusions. The introduction of PRP parabolbar is recommended to be carried out 2-3 times a week, in the amount of 3-4 procedures, depending on the severity of the process. Platelet-rich autoplasm, when administered, accelerates tissue regeneration and reduces inflammation. To get faster results, it is better to start treatment from the first day of the patient's hospitalization.

The use of PRP in HK therapy allows for faster and more lasting results compared to patients receiving standard treatment. The technique is safe, does not cause toxic or allergic reactions, and does not require the use of preservatives. These features ensure good drug tolerance. The procedure is characterized by accessibility, ease of execution and low cost.

Literature

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